

COVID-19 Vaccination Status among the Students of a Non-Government Medical College in Chattogram City

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Abstract

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh is part of the worldwide pandemic of Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). Medical students are among frontline healthcare providers likely to be exposed to COVID-19 patients. The aim of the study to evaluate the medical student's knowledge about COVID-19 Vaccine.

Materials and methods: The cross-sectional study was carried out to explore the Covid -19 vaccination status among the students of Chattagram International Medical College in Chattogram. The study period was from October to December, 2021. A total of 125 students were interviewed for the study and a non-probability sampling technique was used. Face to face interview method was applied for data collection by using pretested, predesigned, semi-structured questionnaires.

Results: The respondents belonged to the age group 19-23 years. The first main result from the study revealed that the vaccination coverage is 100% among the students of Chattagram International Medical College. The pain was the most commonly observed side effect (66%) following vaccination. Another important finding from our study revealed that 100% of study subjects wore masks, followed by 92% continued frequent hand wash. But only 56% maintained social distancing, which is quite regressive.

Conclusion: COVID-19 vaccination program should be implemented across the country to reduce the global burden of illness and death and preventive activities that have to be followed strictly to fight the deadliest disease in the 21st century.

Key words: COVID-19; COVID-19 vaccine; Pandemic.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, also known as the coronavirus pandemic, is an ongoing global pandemic of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) caused by Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona Virus 2 (SARS-CoV-2). The novel virus was first identified in the Chinese city of Wuhan in December 2019, a lockdown there and in other cities is surrounding Hubei failed to contain the outbreak.¹ The world health organization (WHO) declared a public health emergency of international concern on 30 January 2020 and a pandemic on March 11, 2020. Multiple variants of the virus emerged, led by the alpha, beta, gamma, delta and omicron variants. As of 12 December 2021 more than 269 million cases and 5.3 million deaths have been confirmed, making pandemic one of the deadliest in the history.² As of 12 December 2021 more than 5.3 had been attributed to COVID-19. Official deaths from COVID-19 generally refer to people who died after testing positive. The first confirmed death was in Wuhan on 9 January 2020. The first reported death outside of China occurred on 1 February 2020 in the Philippines, The first reported death outside Asia was in the United States on 6 February 2020.^{3,4} People at the greatest risk of mortality from COVID-19 are the elderly (age 65 years or older) and those with underlying conditions.⁵ The COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh is part of the worldwide pandemic of corona virus disease 2019 COVID-19.⁵ The virus was confirmed to have spread to Bangladesh in March 2020. The first three known cases were reported on 8 March 2020 by the country's epidemiology institute, IEDCR. Since then, the pandemic has spread day by day over the whole nation and the number of affected people has been increasing. Bangladesh is the second most affected country in South Asia after India: On 8 March the first three corona virus

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cases were confirmed.⁶ They included two men that recently returned from Italy and a female relative. On 18 March, Bangladesh reported its first corona virus death.⁷ The patient was aged over 70 and had other morbidities. By the end of March Bangladesh had reported 51 confirmed cases and five deaths. On 21 December 2020, the European Union approved the Pfizer Bio N'Tech vaccine H. Vaccinations began to be administered on 27 December 2020. The Moderna vaccine was authorized on 6 January 2021. The AstraZeneca vaccine was authorized on 29 January 2021. On 8 December, it was reported that the AstraZeneca vaccine is about 70% effective, according to a study. As of mid-August 2021, more than 4.6 billion doses of COVID-19 vaccines had been administered in over 190 countries.

The Oxford-AstraZeneca vaccine was the most widely used.⁸ Bangladesh began the administration of COVID-19 vaccines on 27 January 2021, focusing initially on a pilot program of 500 health workers, while mass vaccination started on 7 February 2021. It was planned that 6 million doses would be administered in the first month and a further 5 million the following month.⁹ An online registration portal was launched where citizens registered using their NID number. Initially, registration was open to those aged 55 and above, but due to lower than expected take-up, this was promptly lowered to ages 40 and above. On 5 July 2021 after the vaccination program had re-opened, DGHS announced the registration age would be lowered to 35 years and then 30 years on 19 July.¹⁰ University vaccination or Univac was launched to vaccinate university students. Since the vaccination minimum age was reduced to 18, but many did not have NID to register at the main government vaccine website (<https://surokkha.gov.bd>) another website (<https://univac.ugc.gov.bd>) was launched to allow university students with birth certificates to register for the vaccine. On November 2nd, the campaign to vaccinate 12-17 year olds in school started. They had to register through their schools to be vaccinated. As of 13 December 2021, 8.47 billion COVID-19 vaccine doses have been administered worldwide, with 56 percent of the global population having received at least one dose. While 34.09 million vaccines were then being administered daily, only 7.1 percent of people in low-income countries had received at

least a first vaccine by December 2021. As of 13 December 2021, 8.47 billion COVID-19 vaccine doses have been administered worldwide, with 56 percent of the global population having received at least one dose. While 34.09 million vaccines were then being administered daily, only 7.1 percent of people in low-income countries had received at least a first vaccine by December 2021.¹¹ The aim of the study to evaluate the medical student's knowledge about COVID-19 Vaccine.

Materials and methods

This cross-sectional survey was conducted using a pre structured questionnaire. Medical students from Chittagong International Medical College were selected to participate through convenience sampling. Questionnaires were distributed to students' and collected data by face to face interview. Prior to the study, the students provided with an informed consent form. All students received information about the study purpose, and they were told that participation was voluntary and anonymous.

Inclusion criteria

- Medical students
- Eligible for COVID-19 vaccines
- Volunteered to participate in this study.

Exclusion criteria

- Infected with COVID-19
- Pregnant or breastfeeding women
- Diagnosed with diseases that prevented them from receiving the COVID-19 vaccines.

In total, 125 medical students completed our questionnaire from October to December 2021. The government of Bangladesh has been providing COVID-19 vaccines for college students since April 2021. Thus, all of the participants in this study have received COVID-19 vaccines. In total, 39 incomplete questionnaires were excluded and finally 125 questionnaires were analyzed. The survey questionnaire contained 3 parts and it took the students approximately 6 minutes to complete the survey. Medical students' demographic characteristics were collected. A self-design, 14-item questionnaire was employed to evaluate the medical students' knowledge about COVID-19 vaccine (e.g. Types of vaccines, vaccination eligibility, common side effects and precautions after vaccination). The questionnaire was developed through a literature review and group discussion. Furthermore, we investigated the sources of students' knowledge about COVID-19 vaccine.

The reasons hindering COVID-19 vaccination among medical students were also investigated (e.g Side effects of vaccine, vaccine safety, convenience, vaccine efficacy and underestimating the risk of exposure to COVID-19). We used IBM SPSS Statistics 22.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, New York) for statistical analysis. The value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

The respondents belonged to the age group 19-23 years. The first main result from the study revealed that the vaccination coverage is 100% among the students of Chattagram International Medical College. The pain was the most commonly observed side effect (56%) following immunization. Another important finding from our study revealed that 100% of study subjects wore masks, followed by 92% continued frequent hand wash. But only 56% maintained social distancing, which is quite regressive.

Table I Distribution of the respondents according to knowledge about newly emerging disease

Knowledge □	Frequency □	Percentage
Yes □	125 □	100%
No □	00 □	00%
Total □	□	100%

Table shows that all respondents knew about the newly emerging diseases (Table I).

Table II Distribution of the respondents according to the source of information

Source of information □	Frequency □	Percentage
Social media □	100 □	80%
Newspaper □	22 □	17.6%
Friends/Family □	3 □	2.4%
Total □	125 □	100%

Table shows that 80% of the respondents obtained the information from social media, followed by 17.6% from newspapers and 2.4% from friends/ family (Table II).

Table III Symptoms followed by COVID infection

Symptoms □	Frequency □	Percentage
Fever □	69 □	55.2%
Pain □	59 □	47.2%
Headache □	35 □	28%
Cough □	3 □	2.4%
Others □	15 □	12%

Table shows that 55.2% of the respondents were suffering from fever, 47.2% from pain, 28% from headache and 2.4% from cough (Table III).

Figure 1 Status of Vaccination

The bar chart shows that all respondents were vaccinated against COVID-19 (Figure 1).

Figure 2 Distribution of the respondents according to complications following vaccination

The bar chart shows that the maximum respondents (66%) experienced local pain followed by 34.4% with fever, 13.6% with body ache and 4% with generalized weakness (Figure 2).

Table IV Distribution of the respondents based on the following preventive measures

Preventive measures □	Frequency □	Percentage
Wearing mask □	125 □	100%
Frequent hand wash □	115 □	92%
Social distancing □	70 □	56%

Table shows that 100% of study subjects wore masks, followed by 92% continued frequent hand wash, but only 56% maintained social distancing (Table IV).

Discussion

In this study, most of the respondents 98.40% were Muslim. This is a reflection of majority of inhabitants of Bangladesh. 56.0% respondents hailed from upper class followed by 37.6% from upper middle class. Among the study participants, 74.4% were from nuclear family and 22.4% from joint family. 100% respondents heard about COVID-19.

A major portion (80%) of them got information about COVID-19 and COVID vaccine through social networking sites where 17.6% respondents knew it from online news. Only a small portion of our study group (12%) was COVID positive. 55.2% respondents suffered from fever, 47.2% from body ache, 28% complained headache. The first main result from the study revealed that, the vaccination coverage is 100% among the students of Chattagram International Medical College. All the participants got vaccinated from Chittagong Medical College. From the report regarding COVID-19 vaccination coverage in 84 medical and dental colleges published by DG Health, we observed that Chattogram International Medical College secured 17th position and our coverage was 94.44% since August. But it is exclaimed with joy that, the percentage of COVID-19 vaccination reached to 100%.

The result is not representing the whole country's vaccination status. Although Our government has started their vaccination strategy and inoculation program with an aim to bring about 80% of the total population under COVID-19 vaccination program but reaching its target is yet to far since till only 54.62% of total population has come under the vaccination program.¹² Moreover, findings of our study is not similar to a study done at university of Sao Paulo medical school, Brazil where overall vaccination rate was 74.7%.¹³

Another study conducted at medical school in southeast Michigan where vaccination coverage was found far from optimal. After receiving the vaccine few minor side effects were observed among the vaccine receiver. Among them, 56% suffered from local pain at the injection sites followed by 26.4% complained fever, 13.6% generalized weakness and 4% cough. These findings were found quiet similar to a prospective observational study with an aim to find out Vaccine side-effects and SARS CoV-2 infection after vaccination in users in the UK.¹⁴ We found another similar findings in a study done at Sheikh Russel Gastro-liver Institute and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, 2021. Pain was the most common observed side effect (54.1%) following immunization.¹⁵ Another important finding from our study revealed that, 100% of study subjects were wearing mask followed by 92 % continued frequent hand wash. but only 56% maintained social distancing which is quite regressive. One study conducted at 6 medical schools of Jordan where >80% of study participant showed positive attitude and practices toward wearing mask and frequent hand wash after vaccination but did not maintain social distance all the time.

Limitations

- The small portion doesn't reflect the overall immunization status of the community.
- Due to a shortage of time, some of the important aspects were not included in the questionnaire.

Conclusion

To conclude, all the study subjects were vaccinated and no serious or lifethreatening vaccine complications were observed. But after vaccination, a large portion of them was not maintaining social distancing. To control the pandemic and save lives, there is no doubt that a safe vaccine is a game changing tool at preventing serious illness, hospitalization and death from all current virus variants. But vaccination alone might not be enough to end the COVID 19 pandemic because it is still under research whether removal of pandemic precautions could lead to an increase in virus spread or not.

So, the COVID-19 Vaccination program should be implemented across the country to reduce the global burden of illness and death. Preventive activities have to be followed strictly to fight the deadliest disease in the 21st century.

Recommendations

- Raising public awareness through mass media.
- Demonstrating positive aspects of vaccination.
- Government, Health providers, public health specialists should encourage the public to accept immunization.
- Mass Vaccination.
- Continue wearing masks, cleaning hands, ensuring good ventilation indoors, physically distancing and avoiding crowds.

Disclosure

Both the authors declared no competing interest.

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